

IMPROVING STUDENTS' LOGICAL LITERACY THROUGH COMBINATORICS PROBLEMS IN PRIMARY GRADE MATHEMATICS LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses effective methods for improving students' logical literacy in mathematics lessons and improving logical literacy through combinatorics problems. The importance of text problems in the development of logical thinking is highlighted and the importance of using problem situations in the educational process is analyzed. During the study, it is substantiated that the formation of logical literacy serves students' deep assimilation of mathematical knowledge. The practical importance of logical, combinatorics and non-standard problems in the formation of literacy is also studied.

Keywords: logical literacy, combinatorics, sets, non-standard problems.

Introduction. Today, one of the most important tasks in the education system is not only to provide students with knowledge, but also to develop their logical thinking, analysis, and reasoning skills. In particular, mathematics serves as a key tool in forming logical literacy in students.

Logical literacy is the student's ability to analyze a given problem or issue, identify cause-and-effect relationships, and draw the right conclusions. Developing students' logical thinking through effective organization of mathematics lessons at the primary and general secondary education levels creates a solid foundation for mastering future subjects.

Text problems form the basis of the content of the mathematics course in primary grades, and the methods of mental activity used in the process of solving them: analysis, synthesis, comparison, analogy, generalization, abstraction and concretization, along with the development of students' logical thinking skills, have a positive effect on cultivating their interest in mathematics. Therefore, the types of text problems in the content of the primary education mathematics curriculum, created on the basis of the requirements of the new State Educational Standard of General Secondary Education, have been expanded, and logical and combinatorial problems have been included in their composition for the first time.

The inclusion of logical problems in the elementary mathematics curriculum is explained,

on the one hand, by the fact that solving these problems has a positive effect on the mental development of students and develops in them the skills to express their thoughts based on logical consistency, and on the other hand, by the fact that in solving these problems, calculations are not required at all or play an auxiliary role, being limited only to information about arithmetic.

Solving combinatorial problems, like logical problems, has a positive effect on the mathematical development of students.

Based on the analysis of situations and situations presented in logical, combinatorial and non-standard problems, students acquire the skills of searching for and separating the necessary information, establish cause-and-effect relationships, build a logical chain of reasoning, and, relying on specific conditions, form and develop the competence of educational activities such as selecting and solving the most convenient and effective methods of solving the problem[4].

Materials and methods In many cases, practical problems arise that have several possible solutions. In order to make the right choice when solving such problems, it is important not to leave any of them out. This requires selecting all possible cases or determining their number. Problems that require such an approach to finding a solution are called combinatorial problems. Therefore, from the point of view of set theory, solving combinatorial problems involves selecting subsets of a set that satisfy certain properties and ordering them[4].

Combinatorial problems are concerned with determining the existence of combinatorial combinations that satisfy given conditions; with determining the number of all possible combinations; and with determining the most optimal possibilities according to given principles.

The basis for solving combinatorial problems is the rules of addition and multiplication. The rule of addition is defined as follows: if object a can be selected in m ways and object b in k ways, then object "a or b" can be selected in $m+k$ ways.

Example: There are 4 pomegranates, 5 pears, and 6 apples in a basket. In how many ways can you choose one fruit from the basket?

Solution: Object 1 has 4,
 object 2 has 5,
 object 3 has 6 $m+k=4+5+6=15$

so there are 15 different fruits that can be chosen.

The multiplication rule is defined as follows: if object a can be chosen in m ways and object b in k ways, then the pair (a,b) can be chosen in $m \cdot k$ ways.

Example: There is white bread, brown bread, and three types of sausages in the school cafeteria. How many different sandwiches can be made from them?

Solution: Object 1 is white bread, black bread, i.e. 2 types.

Object 2 is sausage, 3 types

$m \cdot k = 2 \cdot 3 = 6$, so 6 types of sandwiches can be prepared.

Other formulas of combinatorics are also derived based on these rules and their results. Therefore, these rules occupy a very important place in combinatorics[5].

Results. Primary school students learn how to solve even complex combinatorial problems using these simple rules, and thus increase their logical thinking skills and logical literacy.

Example: There are 4 pomegranates, 5 pears, and 6 apples in a basket. In how many ways can you choose two different fruits from the basket? In this problem, you need to use the addition and multiplication rules together:

Solution: two different fruits, namely from the basket:

pomegranate, pear according to the multiplication rule $4 \cdot 5 = 20$

pomegranate, apple $4 \cdot 6 = 24$

pear, apple $5 \cdot 6 = 30$

according to the addition rule: $20 + 24 + 30 = 74$

Answer: There are 74 ways to choose two different fruits?

Above, we looked at the methods for solving combinatorial problems using the addition and multiplication rules. However, these methods cannot be directly applied to solving combinatorial problems in elementary grades. In elementary grades, when solving problems of this type, methods of selecting all possible cases are considered (such a solution method does not require the use of formulas and knowledge of definitions). Therefore, in solving

problems of this type, the main attention is paid directly to the process of constructing various combinations, and not to determining how many solutions there are to the problem, but to determining what possibilities are formed. To do this, students will need to correctly and quickly find all possible possibilities, as well as show that there are no other possibilities. When solving elementary combinatorial problems, students select the objects required by the problem condition randomly, in a random manner. Therefore, it is important for students to make sure that all the combinations required by the problem condition are found. To do this, it is advisable to visually represent the solutions to the initial problems in the form of drawings, the number of which exceeds the number of all possible combinations, and ask students to answer based on coloring the drawings. As a result, students find a solution to the problem by coloring the drawings that satisfy the answer and can explain that the drawings that are not colored are superfluous. Through these methods, students gain a deeper understanding of mathematics and increase their logical literacy. This also serves as a foundation for solving complex combinatorial problems in the future.

Conclusion. Improving students' logical literacy in mathematics lessons is one of the important factors in improving the quality of education. The study of logical, combinatorial and non-standard problems is of great importance in improving logical literacy. The ability to apply simple combinatorial problems in practical activities is formed from the primary grades. The introduction of logical problems from the primary grades, and the solution of these problems, has a positive impact on the intellectual development of students, developing in them the skills to express their thoughts based on logical consistency.

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